

**ORGANIZING THE TECHNICAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS
ON THE BASIS OF AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH**

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Further improvement of the continuous education system, development of the policy of training qualified personnel and the system of measures to strengthen the material and technical base of education, the training of pedagogues and staff in our Republic and the process of pedagogical education are qualitatively new the issue of raising to the next level has been identified as one of the priorities for the modernization and further development of the society.

President of our Republic Sh. In Mirziyoev's words, "We will mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our state and society so that our young people can become independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field in the world, and become happy."

The successful solution of these tasks requires the harmony of theory and practice. That is why it is very important to organize the qualification practice in higher education institutions at a high level in all respects.

For this purpose, improving the knowledge and initial skills acquired by the future pedagogue personnel in theoretical training, while integrally connecting them to the professional practice process, is important in the formation of professional competence.

In N.A. Muslimov's scientific research work, professional competence is explained as follows:

"Competence is expressed by the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of professional activities of personal and social importance and their application in professional activities."

Currently, formation of professional competences of students studying in Higher Pedagogical Educational Institutions is dependent only on theory. Because professional competence is manifested in practical activities. For this, we found it appropriate to establish and scientifically substantiate the integration of specialized sciences and professional practice on the basis of a competent approach, so that students can apply the knowledge, skills and qualifications obtained from specialized subjects to professional practice and develop their professional competencies. Therefore, it is necessary to organize the integration of specialized subjects and professional practice on the basis of a competent approach to reveal the content of practice. To do this, expand the content of professional practice; We determined that the following processes should be activated in order to isolate and master the important concepts in it:

- organizing the integration of specialized sciences and professional practice based on a competent approach, reducing the likelihood of a subjective approach to determining the situation;
- drawing students' attention to aspects that are important in revealing the important problems of professional practice;
- to constantly expand students' creative initiative and independence of professional practice activities, to organize this integration based on a competent approach, to apply various didactic tools and to carry out organizational work on its use step by step;
- creating creative cooperation between teachers and students;

- formation of students' professional competence qualities, scientific worldview based on the requirements of the present time, in harmony with social life through this means of integration.

Ensuring the organization of the integration of specialized subjects and professional practice in higher education institutions based on a competent approach helps to systematize the knowledge of students, to form their independent thinking skills and abilities, and to deepen the knowledge acquired at the lower levels of education.

This process forms and enriches students' perceptions of the environment, people, nature and society. Based on them, the task of summarizing the knowledge acquired from the subjects is solved effectively.

Students develop their knowledge with the help of basic concepts and terms in the process of mastering specialized subjects.

We believe that it is necessary to improve the professional practice process in the system of specialized sciences based on the function of organizing the integration of specialized sciences and professional practice on the basis of a competent approach, on the basis of mastering and developing the concepts that form the basis of modern knowledge, based on the following tasks:

- the content richness and generality of the competence, formation of the worldview of students as a form of knowledge with the help of this integration, increasing the efficiency of their knowledge acquisition process;

- the competence function of the integration of professional practice, determining the important directions of improving the professional practice that can meet the social requirements of the student's development;

- as a result of ensuring this integration, creating favorable conditions for the use of modern pedagogical and innovative technologies in the process of professional practice.

This integration is manifested as an opportunity to synthesize the knowledge of students from different fields and develop their professional competence.

This integration envisages the formation of the skills of perception in a generalized form, the development of students' ability to generalize their acquired knowledge, to perceive a single generality, to evaluate events;

- this integration allows students to form scientific outlooks.

- this integration helps to ensure systematicity in professional practice.

Students can perform the methodological tasks of acquiring knowledge in the professional practice only if they understand this integration and demonstrate their professional competence.

The general structure and elements of academic subjects create the following objective bases for the implementation of this integration in practice:

- acquired knowledge, understanding and evidence;

- laws and theories;

- concepts that shape the student's outlook;

- historical problems and the path of development of science;

- methodological foundations and methods of science;

- specified special skills and qualifications;

- scientific methodical supply of science;

- ideological and educational aspects of the presented knowledge.

This integration, which is implemented on a regular basis, helps to acquire knowledge related to various fields, and their constant use also helps to strengthen the acquired skills and competencies of students.

It increases their interest in learning and the efficiency of the process. This integration is one of the didactic possibilities of acquiring knowledge and organizing professional practice.

It is carried out based on the methods of practice determined as the basis for forming and developing students' competence.

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